

Effects of mixing assumptions and models for LES of Hydrogen-fueled Rotating Detonation Engines

P. Strempl^{a,*}, O. Dounia^a, D. Laera^{a,c}, T. Poinsot^{a,b}

^a*CERFACS, 42 Avenue Gaspard Coriolis, 31057 Toulouse, France*

^b*Institut de Mécanique des Fluides de Toulouse, IMFT, Université de Toulouse, CNRS, 31400 Toulouse, France*

^c*Dipartimento di Meccanica, Matematica e Management, Politecnico di Bari, Via Orabona 4, 70125, Bari, Italy*

Abstract

Large Eddy Simulations (LES) are a powerful tool to analyze the flow in Rotating Detonation Engines, but their implementation is not straightforward. Many groups use simplifications (perfect premixing, geometrical 2D representations of the chamber) and numerical high-fidelity analysis comparing mixing assumptions in full scale configurations are not commonly found in literature. In this work a 3D LES of a full RDE tested at TU Berlin is performed and the influence of mixing assumptions (fully premixed vs. non-premixed) and sub-grid scale models on the detonation propagation are investigated. Simulations show that premixed RDEs burn more fuel in a detonation regime, resulting in a faster detonation wave than in the non-premixed case, while a change in the sub-grid-scale model does not lead to significant changes. LES reveals that all cases lose a high amount of fuel

*Corresponding author
strempl@cerfacs.fr
Tel.:+33 (0) 5 61 19 31 19

to non-detonative combustion. These results show, that mixing plays a significant role in the LES of RDEs and has to be included to increase the accuracy of the simulations. The importance of deflagration in the overall RDE combustor implies, that chemistry models need to account for deflagration properties as well as for detonation to capture the efficiency of RDEs.

Keywords: Rotating detonation engine, Hydrogen, Mixing, Large Eddy Simulation, Sub-grid scale models

1. Introduction

In the search of more efficient combustion systems, detonation-based combustion has become a candidate for future applications in rocket engines and gas turbines due to its theoretically higher thermodynamic efficiency [1, 2]. The Rotating Detonation Engine (RDE) is an engine concept using a rotating detonation and research on these engines has intensified in the recent years. Conceptually, in RDEs a self sustained detonation propagates azimuthally in an e.g. annular combustion chamber leading to a pressure increase due to the detonation process. Various studies have been conducted on hydrogen powered RDEs, focusing especially on the detonation propagation and wave modes [3–5], occurrence of instabilities [6–8] and ignition [9]. Besides the typical cylindrical annular combustion chamber, other concepts of RDEs exist, such as RDEs with hollow combustion chambers [10] or disc type RDEs [11]. While a lot of research is conducted on fully gaseous setups (such as in this work), numerical [12–14] and experimental [15–17] research on RDEs with liquid fuel is also intensifying. These multi-phase setups contain additional complexities such as atomization, evaporation or shock-droplet interaction.

Numerical simulations are important tools to further analyze this novel type of engines. In many cases, the configuration of the RDE is simplified either by considering a planar periodic chamber [8, 12, 13, 18–21], by eliminating injection systems [18, 22–27] or assuming a periodic slot [28]. Although numerical simulations of realistic 3D configurations have been conducted including all the feeding systems for fuel and air (thanks to increasing

computational resources and performance) [29–34], there are still only a few examples of full LES of RDEs [35–38], although they are superior in modeling turbulent mixing structures.

Here, we consider only full three-dimensional RDE chambers including all the injection lines of fuel (hydrogen here) and air from the plenums which feed a cylindrical chamber. From a point of view of simulation, these cases gather multiple difficulties which have eluded the LES community for decades:

(1) RDEs use detonation waves and the simulation of detonations in complex systems remains a basic unsolved problem in the combustion community for multiple reasons. The major one is the usual curse of resolution needs in three dimensions: very few groups are able to handle the three-dimensional meshes which would be required to simulate detonations in many cases, so that a significant part of the fundamental studies of detonations are performed in two dimensions, e.g. [39–42]. The high resolution is necessary for capturing the correct detonation cell structure, which is detrimental for the stability of a detonation. The existence of shock interactions and extreme pressures and temperatures also makes their numerical treatment additionally difficult when it is coupled to chemistry. Additionally, RDEs are fully three dimensional and often involve numerous small jets, which add very heavy meshing constraints.

(2) A second specificity of detonation is the difficulty of using reliable, high-precision kinetic schemes. The question of the right chemical scheme to use in simulations of detonation remains open: while certain authors eg.

[43–45] try to use complex chemistry schemes for H_2 -air combustion, others use simple, reduced schemes [25–27, 46–50].

(3) RDE flows gather shocks as well as mixing and chemical reaction zones. Precise shock treatments are obviously mandatory to handle detonations. These treatments involve some type of numerical limiters as seen in [51, 52] to ensure monotonicity in the shock region. On top of that, most of the currently investigated configurations are jet-in-crossflow setups (e.g.[53]), where fuel is injected into an oxidizer crossflow including another level of complexity. It has been shown by numerous groups that a proper investigation of a jet-in-crossflow represents a challenge in itself [54–58], potentially adding complexity to shock and mixing structures. This usually comes at the cost of additional numerical viscosity and artificial dissipation, being clearly detrimental in the mixing zones, which are also critical for RDE since this is the place where fuel and oxidizer must mix in a reduced time (less than one rotation of the detonation wave), in zones where high speed jets interact with each other at high Reynolds numbers and subsequently interact with the passing detonation wave. The existence of shock interactions and extreme pressures and temperatures at these points also makes their numerical treatment additionally difficult when it is coupled to chemistry.

(4) While most fundamental studies of detonation focus on pure detonation, RDEs may involve simultaneously zones of detonation and of deflagration, also often named "parasitic" combustion [32, 33, 59]. While the precision of molecular transport models is not of utmost importance for the

global propagation of a detonation, it is critical for deflagration so that the codes performing LES of RDE must be able to compute both deflagration and detonation on the same mesh with the same sub-models for chemistry and numerical parameters.

(5) Finally, RDE flows involve multiple walls and high Reynolds numbers so that the wall treatment itself becomes an issue: using wall-law models may be needed but might deteriorate accuracy.

The objective of this work is to analyze the influence of mixing assumptions and sub-grid scale models on the detonation propagation and combustion efficiency of the system, to determine the necessity of modeling the mixing process in a RDE. The conducted LES on one fixed experimental setup allow to clearly identify mixing losses and their underlying mechanisms by highlighting the refill and mixing performance of the injection system. This paper is organized the following sections: Sec. 2 introduces the test rig, Sec. 3 explains the conducted runs, Sec. 4 elaborates on the numerical modeling, Sec. 5 illustrates the diagnostic tools, Sec. 6 discusses the results and Sec. 7 concludes the paper.

2. Configuration: the TU Berlin RDE

This work conducts a numerical simulation of the non-premixed RDC test rig installed at TU Berlin, composed of an annular combustion chamber with a width of 7.6 mm and an inner radius of 37.4 mm , leading to an outer diameter of 90 mm . The chamber walls are straight, the combustor

blows directly into the atmosphere and has no outlet restriction. At the bottom of the chamber is a discrete injection system, composed of 100 equally distributed H_2 injectors with a diameter of 0.5 mm . Air is injected via a radially inward leading air gap, creating a cross-flow for the H_2 jets. The H_2 injectors as well as the air gap are undivided from their respective plenums, where piezo-resistive sensors are monitoring the plenum pressures. The operating conditions of the experimental run are listed in Table 1: all reference experimental data have been obtained directly from the research team at TU Berlin.

Figure 1: Sketch of the RDE test rig installed at TUB. Adapted from [60].

H_2 mass flow	<i>g/s</i>	13.7
<i>Air</i> mass flow	<i>g/s</i>	517.7
H_2 temperature	<i>K</i>	287
<i>Air</i> temperature	<i>K</i>	287
H_2 plenum pressure	<i>bar</i>	11.2
Air plenum pressure	<i>bar</i>	5.2
Equivalence ratio	-	0.9

Table 1: Operational conditions of the investigated experimental setup. The displayed data has been directly obtained from the research team of TUB.

3. Test cases

The geometrical meshing constraints of a full RDE configuration (chamber but also injection systems) can be difficult to satisfy in LES: the first one in the TUB configuration is the existence of 100 H_2 jets in cross-flow into the main air stream. For this configuration called here 'CASE2', mixing plays a role. It can be computed, but it comes at a high cost and with significant modeling approximations (for the sub-grid scale diffusivity models for example). Obviously, the temptation to assume perfect premixing of fuel with the incoming air is great as it simplifies the simulation. At the same time, all issues associated with mixing are also suppressed, making the simulation probably less valuable. This 'PERFECTLY MIXED' option, called 'CASE1', remains interesting however, especially since it allows to quantify the importance of mixing models in the simulation. No mixing system can work better than what the 'PERFECTLY MIXED' option can achieve. The difference between CASE1 and CASE2 in a realistic configuration must be explored. The change of composition in the plenum changes the velocity in

the injectors, however this does not impact the overall refill behavior (see Sec. 6.2). As mentioned in Sec. 4.6, the second influence on the mixing performance is the SGS model. A comparison between two SGS models allows to evaluate their influence on the mixing process. For this purpose a third simulation, 'CASE3', is conducted and evaluated. Table 2 lists the three runs and their specificities. The quantity z_{nom} denotes the nominal mixture fraction ([61]), if the gases are ideally mixed.

RUN	MIXING	SGS	\dot{m}_{H_2}	\dot{m}_{Air}	$z_{nom} = \frac{\dot{m}_{H_2}}{\dot{m}_{Air} + \dot{m}_{H_2}}$
NAME	CONFIGURATION	MODEL	[g/s]	[g/s]	[-]
CASE1	PREMIXED	WALE	13.7	517.7	0.0258
CASE2	NON-PREMIXED	WALE	13.7	517.7	0.0258
CASE3	NON-PREMIXED	SIGMA	13.7	517.7	0.0258

Table 2: Summary of LES runs.

4. Numerical setup

4.1. Code and numerical models

The simulations are performed with the cell-vertex finite-volume AVBP 7.12 code of CERFACS [62]. The numerical scheme is Lax-Wendroff (LW) [63], due to the acceptable trade-off between accuracy and time costs. It is of second-order accuracy in time and space. The sub-grid stresses are modeled via the WALE or the SIGMA model (, further explained in Sec. 4.6). The fluid is considered a perfect gas and localized artificial diffusivity [52] is applied in regions of strong gradients. The laminar viscosity is computed via

a power-law

$$\mu_{lam} = \mu_{ref}(T/T_{ref})^{0.686} \quad (1)$$

with $\mu_{ref} = 1.833\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}\times 10^{-5}$ and $T_{ref} = 300\text{K}$. The turbulent Schmidt- and Prandtl number are set to $Sc_t = 0.6$ and $Pr_t = 0.6$. All simulations are explicit in time and limited by the CFL number.

4.2. Meshing strategy

Figure 2 illustrates the topology of the mesh used in this study: It is a purely tetrahedral mesh with local mesh size Δ . The H_2 injectors have a cell size of $50\mu\text{m}$, corresponding to $d_{H_2}/\Delta_{H_2} = 10$, which ensures a proper resolution in the H_2 -injectors. The cells in the air gap are $160\mu\text{m}$, corresponding $d_{Air}/\Delta_{Airslot} = 11$, thereby ensuring a proper resolution of the air slot. The cross flow is discretized by elements of $100\mu\text{m}$ (dot-dashed box in Fig. 2) to resolve the mixing in the crossflow. In the lower chamber (without the dashed box) a resolution of $140\mu\text{m}$, which corresponds to the expected $\delta_{1/2}$, is chosen to further resolve the mixing process, the turbulent eddies and the detonation. For the LES of deflagrations, the number of points should be typically around 5-10 points across the flame front [64]. Recent numerical studies show that 3D detonation fronts in non-ideal conditions representative of RDEs are much thicker than their 1D counterpart, hence mesh sizes of the order of the detonation half reaction thickness $\delta_{1/2}$ (see Sec. 4.4) are often used [35–38]. Further downstream, the lower chamber is followed by a coarser area of $400\mu\text{m}$ and a coarse area of $760\mu\text{m}$ to attenuate minor oscillations at

the outlet. This results in a mesh with overall 260M tetrahedrals grid cells.

Figure 2: Cut of a mesh section and local target grid sizes.

4.3. Boundary conditions

The inlet and outlet boundary conditions are imposed via the NSCBC formalism [65]. At the inlets the mass flow is imposed, since the initial plenum conditions are a result of the imposed mass flow in the experiments. The outlet is treated as a pressure outlet at 1 atm, since the combustor blows into the atmosphere. Under the assumption of a very low mach number at the inlets, the static temperature at the inlets is assumed equal to the measured static plenum temperature. All walls are treated as adiabatic slip walls.

4.4. Chemistry model

In the present work, a 1-step reversible global mechanism 1S-Deto is applied to model the chemical reactions. 1S-Deto contains four species, namely: H_2 , O_2 , N_2 , H_2O . The reaction is modeled as:

and the progress of reaction Eq. 2 is computed by an Arrhenius law. The model parameters are optimized for an equivalence ratio of $\phi = 0.9$ and ambient conditions. Matching the Chapman-Jouguet speed requires a small increase of the enthalpy of formation of H_2O , $\Delta H_f^{0K}(H_2O)$ by 12 kJ/kg . This compensates the effect of dissociation compared to a detailed mechanism. The Arrhenius constant A and the activation energy are obtained by targeting the $\delta_{1/2}$ computed via Mevel [66, 67]. 1S-Deto delivers a correct CJ (Chapman Jouguet) speed and is built to capture the correct detonation half reaction thickness $\delta_{1/2}$. Table 3 presents and compares the chemical scheme 1S-Deto to detailed chemistry schemes (San Diego [68] and Mevel). It has been evaluated for detonations in the range $\phi = 0.4$ to 1.8, but also for deflagration for $\phi = 0.4$ to 3 . 1S-Deto is optimized by comparing to the mechanism of Mevel.

Figure 3 shows the performances of scheme 1S-Deto compared to the Mevel and San Diego scheme, in the following called UCSD. The displayed mechanisms match well in term of D_{cj} . The main differences can be seen

Name	Parameters at $\phi = 0.9$
1S-Deto	$D_{cj} = 1925 \text{ m/s}$ $\delta_{1/2} = 149.6 \mu\text{m}$
Mevel	$D_{cj} = 1932 \text{ m/s}$ $\delta_{1/2} = 147.0 \mu\text{m}$
San Diego	$D_{cj} = 1929 \text{ m/s}$ $\delta_{1/2} = 215 \mu\text{m}$

Table 3: Comparison of chemical schemes for the investigated properties at $P_{init} = 1\text{bar}$ and $T_{init} = 300\text{K}$.

Figure 3: CJ detonation speed over equivalence ratio (a) and $\delta_{1/2}$ over equivalence ratio (b) for an initial pressure of 1bar and an initial temperature of 300K .

in the obtained $\delta_{1/2}$ thickness. The San Diego mechanism predicts a significantly higher $\delta_{1/2}$ value compared to Mevel. Since 1S-Deto was derived from Mevel, it delivers $\delta_{1/2}$ values of similar magnitude. For low equivalence ratios ($\phi < 0.9$) however, it gives a smaller $\delta_{1/2}$, while on the other hand for an equivalence ratio of $\phi > 0.9$, $\delta_{1/2}$ has a similar slope as its reference. It is important to note that the choice of a reference mechanism is still up

to debate. Gallier et al. [69] derived a reduced mechanism via Mevel while others e.g. Nassini et al. [38] develop a mechanism referencing Boivin et al. [70], which is a reduction of the UCSD mechanism.

Figure 4: Laminar flame speed s_L of 1S-Deto compared to the San Diego and Mevel mechanism for an initial pressure of $1bar$ and an initial temperature of $300K$.

Since this study aims to also take the consumption of fuel due to deflagration into account, 1S-Deto must also predict the correct laminar flame speed, at least in the relevant range of equivalence ratio ϕ (Fig. 4). This has been done by decreasing the Prandtl number to $Pr = 0.32$, which does not affect D_{cj} or $\delta_{1/2}$. For $\phi > 1.5$ the laminar flame speed is slightly overestimated. Around the design point $\phi = 0.9$ the laminar flame speed s_L^0 is very well matched and all relevant parameters D_{cj} , $\delta_{1/2}$ and s_L are predicted in a satisfying manner. The deflagration properties were obtained via CANTERA [71] and the detonation properties were computed with the CANTERA-based Shock and Detonation Toolbox [72].

n_{H_2}	1
n_{O_2}	0.5
E_a	18000.0 [cal/mol]
A	5.3×10^{10}
$\Delta H_f^{0K}(H_2O)$	-226.8 [kJ/mol]

Table 4: Parameters of the 1S-Deto chemical scheme

4.5. Initialisation

Starting a RDE simulation is an issue in itself, because the initial field may not be good enough to lead to a stable rotating detonation. In this study LES runs are initialized as follows: the simulation CASE1 is initialized by first computing a non reacting cold flow to obtain converged plenum temperatures and pressures. After this test phase, while keeping the plenum and injector conditions, the flow field in the annulus is replaced by a perfectly premixed field and an initial detonation front. This is done by obtaining a 1D ZND detonation profile via CANTERA for an initial $\phi = 0.9$, $T_{init} = 300.0K$, $P_{init} = 1bar$ and extending it with a quadratic expansion towards the reference initial pressure P_{init} over half a circumference (Fig. 5). It is assumed that the azimuthal velocity decreases in the same manner in order to mimic the expansion after the wave. The local temperature is obtained via the following expression:

$$T_{expansion} = T_{cj} \left(\frac{P_{expansion}}{P_{cj}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma_{cj}-1}{\gamma_{cj}}} \quad (3)$$

This ensures a reasonable temperature distribution. Since the initial ex-

Figure 5: Initial temperature and pressure distribution of CASE1 at 33% span of the combustion chamber.

pansion region is supposed to be burnt, the mass fraction of H_2 and O_2 are set to zero and the area is "filled" with only H_2O and N_2 . A flow field of a RDE typically shows a triangular or quadratic refill zone, which needs to be accounted for as well. A quadratic refill area along half the circumference is included after the detonation front to mimic the refill process.

CASE2 is then initialized by obtaining a converged cold flow and inserting the converged reactive solution of CASE1 into the chamber. This is done since a more realistic initial solution is available after running CASE1, requiring less cycles to obtain a stable, converged run.

4.6. Sub-grid scale models

In a LES solver, mixing is controlled by is the sub-grid scale viscosity ν_t , which is imposed via the SGS model chosen for the computation. ν_t controls the turbulent diffusivity D_t :

$$D_t = \frac{\nu_t}{Sc_t}, \quad (4)$$

where Sc_t is a turbulent Schmidt number, assumed to be constant here. D_t drives mixing and can be an important parameter for the LES of CASE2. Two well known SGS models for LES are the WALE [73] and SIGMA [74] models. The SGS model provides an evaluation of ν_t : the approach is to model the sub-grid stresses by introducing ν_t :

$$\nu_t = (C_m \Delta)^2 D_m(\vec{u}), \quad (5)$$

where C_m is a model constant, Δ is the characteristic length scale of the grid, which is in practice the mesh size and D_m is a model dependent differential operator, applied on the resolved velocity field \vec{u} . For WALE the differential operator is a function of the traceless symmetric part of the square of the velocity tensor \mathcal{S}_{ij}^d and the strain rate S_{ij}

$$D_{m,WALE} = \frac{(\mathcal{S}_{ij}^d \mathcal{S}_{ij}^d)^{3/2}}{(S_{ij} S_{ij})^{5/2} + (\mathcal{S}_{ij}^d \mathcal{S}_{ij}^d)^{5/2}}, \quad (6)$$

where C_m becomes the constant $C_{m,WALE}$, obtained via canonical tests and comparisons with experiments, typically about $C_{m,WALE} = 0.5$. For SIGMA the differential operator $D_{m,SIGMA}$ is computed as

$$D_{m,SIGMA} = \frac{\sigma_3(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)(\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)}{\sigma_1^2}, \quad (7)$$

where σ_{1-3} denote the velocity tensor invariances obtained from the resolved velocity field [74]. Here $C_{m,SIGMA}$ is typically around 1.35.

Both SGS models are developed for wall bounded flows, where the cubic behavior of ν_t close to walls is upheld. WALE and SIGMA usually lead to different fields of ν_t and comparing the two models allows to check their influence of the SGS model.

5. Diagnostics

Gathering experimental information for RDEs is difficult. Typical experimental data include the detonation wave speed D obtained via pressure measurements and stagnation pressure measurements at the exit of the combustor [5, 60, 75]. Measuring the static pressure at the walls directly is problematic, since the high pressure and heat loads would damage the sensors. This leads to either measuring the pressure in a recessed cavity (to protect the sensors), or via Capillary Tube Average Pressure (CTAP) measure. Due to the capillary tube however, the pressure signal gets attenuated introducing an error in the measured signal, so that we will rely mainly on pressure signals providing the wave speed.

In addition to D , it is important to analyze the flow topology in details for each run in order to understand the effects of mixing. To do this, the following diagnostics of the LES data will be introduced: First, to understand the mixing process, we introduce the mixing index I_{mix} : it is composed of $Y_{H_2}Y_{O_2}$, which is normalized to build the I_{mix} , based on the definition of the mixture fraction z [61]. If z is known, the local maximum H_2 and O_2 mass fractions can be obtained by the usual mixing rules $Y_{H_2}^m = zY_{H_2}^0$ and

$Y_{O_2}^m = Y_{O_2}^0(1 - z)$ and we construct

$$I_{mix} = \frac{Y_{H_2}Y_{O_2}}{Y_{H_2}^mY_{O_2}^m} = \frac{Y_{H_2}Y_{O_2}}{z_{nom}Y_{H_2}^0Y_{O_2}^0(1 - z_{nom})}, \quad (8)$$

with $z_{nom} = 0.0258$ (Tab. 2) so that $I_{mix} = 1$ for an ideal mixture for CASE1-CASE3. For a perfectly mixed case (CASE1), I_{mix} is constant, because the mixing process is completed and the fuel/oxidizer ratio fixed. For a non-premixed case, the index varies and gives information on the degree of mixing.

¹

Second, we defined the combustion Efficiency E as:

$$E = 1 - \frac{\dot{m}_{fuel}^{out}}{\dot{m}_{fuel}^{in}} \quad (9)$$

where \dot{m}_{fuel}^{out} is the mass flow rate of fuel leaving the chamber at its outlet and \dot{m}_{fuel}^{in} is the nominal inlet mass flow rate of the fuel. E determines how much fuel has burnt within the chamber. To separate the two burning modes, detonation and deflagration, we will introduce a local detonation index I_{det} , which indicates, if local combustion occurs in a deflagration or a detonation front. To build such an index, the approach is to check for all zones where the fuel source term $\dot{\omega}_k$ is significant and to check for the presence of high pressures, indicating if a detonation mode is present or not 'around' the local

¹ I_{mix} is built to reach 1 when all gases are mixed for CASE1 to 3. It can reach values larger than unity during the mixing process, when z goes to 0.5, for which $I_{mix}^{max} = \frac{0.5*0.5}{0.0258*(1-0.0258)} = 10$

point. As an example, Elasma et al.[76] propose a CEMA based approach where the reaction modes are distinguished by comparing a characteristic Damköhler number of the H radical in a detonation and a deflagration. Here we propose a semi-empirical definition for a local detonation index I_{det} :

$$I_{det} = S_{\omega} S_{\bar{P}} \quad (10)$$

with S_{ω} defined as

$$S_{\omega} = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \tanh \left(\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma} \frac{|\dot{\omega}_{fuel}|}{|\dot{\omega}_{fuel,1D}^{max,Deflag}|} - 1 \right) a \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

and $S_{\bar{P}}$ is defined as

$$S_{\bar{P}} = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \tanh \left(\left(\frac{P}{P_{cj,input}} - 1 \right) a \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

Eq. (11) denotes the sensor S_{ω} that flags reactions in a detonation regime based on the local fuel reaction rate and the corresponding maximum reaction rate for a deflagration $\dot{\omega}_{fuel,1D}^{max,Deflag}$. $\dot{\omega}_{fuel,1D}^{max,Deflag}$ is tabulated for a given reference initial condition, here $P_{init} = 1bar$ and $T_{init} = 300K$ and a representative range of ϕ . To account for varying pressures e.g. locally reflected pressure waves at walls higher reaction rates are to be assumed. Hence the second sensor (Eq. (12)) is included, a function of the pressure field P , wide enough to capture a shock if it is 'close' to the flame. This is done by computing the ratio of the local pressure P and a representative $P_{cj,input}$.

The factor Γ is used to amplify $\dot{\omega}_{fuel,1D}^{max,Deflag}$, to account for local deflagration for $1bar \leq P \leq P_{cj,input}$, so that e.g. potential reactions in the wake of a detonation are excluded. The sensor parameter Γ is obtained via multiple calibration iterations on a canonical 2D premixed detonation configuration, which results in $P_{cj,input} = 9bar$ and $\Gamma = 50$. The proportionality factor $a \gg 1$ in Eq. (11) and (12) narrows the transition between deflagration and detonation regions, leading to a quasi step-function, so that S_ω and $S_{\bar{P}}$ are either 0 or 1 ($a = 1000$ for all cases). The product of the two sensors forms I_{det} , shown in Fig. 6 for CASE1.

Once a detonation local criterion I_{det} is computed, it can be used to build a global deflagration based fuel source term:

$$\dot{\Omega}_{defl} = \int_V \dot{\omega}_k (1 - I_{det}) dV \quad (13)$$

as well as a detonation global reaction rate:

$$\dot{\Omega}_{det} = \int_V \dot{\omega}_k I_{det} dV \quad (14)$$

A detonation efficiency E_{det} is then obtained with

$$E_{det} = \dot{\Omega}_{det} / \dot{\Omega}_{tot} \quad (15)$$

The efficiency E_{det} allows to see which parameters affect the way detonation proceeds in the RDE.

Finally the instantaneous fields of temperature and Y_{H_2} will be plotted and compared, including the mixing index I_{mix} to track mixing between the H_2 jets and air. Additionally, the phase-averaged structure of the same fields will be produced by averaging results in a reference frame moving at the speed of the detonation wave, based on 150 snapshots taken during one revolution, once the simulation is in steady operating mode.

6. Results

6.1. Wave speed

In this work the pressure signal of one probe, positioned 25mm above the bottom plate, is used to obtain the wave speed D . The pressure signals are shown in Fig. 7. The detonation speed and wave modes of CASE1, CASE2 and CASE3 are displayed in Tab. 5, D is computed as $2\pi r_{max} * f_{deto}$, since the experimental measurements are taken from the outer wall.

The detonation speed in simulations is often over-predicted in one wave mode setups [36, 38, 77], showing that the deviation from the experimentally measured wave speed can increase with the nominal mass flow rate. The over-prediction can be seen in the present LES, too, with CASE1 displaying the fastest wave speed. The reason for this phenomenon is not trivial to determine and still the topic of ongoing work. CASE1 is especially interesting in this regard, since the detonation is not exposed to a stratified mixture (due to mixing), which has been shown to decrease the detonation speed as well as changing the detonation structure [78].

Figure 6: a) Instantaneous solution of CASE1. The temperature field along the inner wall is displayed, to visualize the domain. Additionally the detonation front is displayed via the iso contour of $I_{det} = 1$ in white. b) an instantaneous cut of CASE1 at 33% span width displaying $I_{det} = 1$ as a white iso contour on the detonation front.

Figure 7: Mid-span pressure signals at $y = 25 \text{ mm}$. The signals are recorded after a steady detonation propagation has been achieved and are sampled at a frequency of 3.8 MHz .

The detonation speed D of CASE1 is about 10% faster than the one in CASE2. Since the difference of the cases lies in the mixing assumption, it can

be concluded that the improved quality of the mixing process in the refill zone of CASE1 leads to an increase in the detonation speed since the mixture can detonate properly. This is in agreement with recently conducted experiments of a variably premixed RDE [79]. In fact, Burke et al. [80] have shown that by additional injection of premixed bypass gases, the detonation speed increases, emphasizing that a slight improvement in the mixture quality amplifies the detonation speed visibly. The variation in maximum pressure of the signals shows that the detonation strength varies during the wave propagation, even in CASE1. However, there is no visible difference in D between CASE2 and CASE3 (Fig. 16). Table 5 lists the different predicted wave speeds versus the experimental one and compares them to the nominal Chapman-Jouguet detonation speed D_{cj} .

	CASE1	CASE2	CASE3	EXPERIMENT
Wave mode [-]	single	single	single	single
Rotation Frequency f_{rot} [Hz]	8280	7630	7630	5800
Detonation wave speed [m/s]	2341	2157	2157	1640
D/D_{cj} [-]	1.216	1.12	1.12	0.85

Table 5: Comparison of the different predicted detonation frequencies with respect to the experimentally obtained wave speed. D_{cj} (=1925 m/s) is based on the nominal $\phi = 0.9$, T_{init} and P_{init} .

6.2. Effects of mixing assumptions: CASE1 vs. CASE2

For the flow fields a general analysis of the instantaneous field is conducted and subsequently a detailed analysis of the phase averaged solution executed. The detonation wave passage results in the slight blockage of mass flow, which

Figure 8: Instantaneous temperature field of CASE1 (a) /CASE2 (b) and instantaneous Y_{H_2} distribution of CASE1 (c) /CASE2 (d) and fields of I_{mix} for CASE1 (e) and CASE2 (f) along 33% span width of the annulus. The black iso contours denote an iso contour of $Y_{H_2} = Y_{H_2,sto}/2$, which delivers a good threshold for the visibility of H_2 pockets.

is seen in Fig. 8 (a)-(f) for $-\pi/2 \leq \Theta \leq 0$. A look at the instantaneous temperature and H_2 fields (Fig. 8 (a)-(d)) shows for all cases the typical flow field structure of a RDE. In front of the detonation wave is a triangular refill zone filled with fresh reactants. Downstream of the detonation an oblique

shock propagates towards the outlet. Between product of the current and previous cycle a slip line is formed.

Compared to CASE1 (Fig. 8 (a)) the temperature distribution in CASE2 (Fig. 8 (b)) shows more local hot spots after the detonation wave, especially in the wake of the foot of the detonation. Although both cases have leftover fuel along the slip line after the detonation (Fig. 8 (c) and (d)), only CASE2 contains multiple fuel pockets in the wake of the detonation and leaves much more fuel to exit the chamber, having a similar refill height as CASE1. The large amount of unburnt H_2 in CASE2 is a first indicator of the importance of mixing in this configuration.

Figure 8 (e) and (f) show the I_{mix} fields of CASE1 and CASE2. The black iso contour identifies pockets of H_2 . Since CASE1 is fully premixed from the beginning, mixing of H_2 and O_2 is almost uniformly constant in the whole refill area with $I_{mix} = 1$ with a few local areas of a dropping I_{mix} , due to the presence of residual combustion products (Fig. 8 (a)). This is not the same for CASE2 where higher values of I_{mix} occur due to the influence of the hydrogen jets at the bottom plate of the chamber. An important distinguishing feature between CASE1 and CASE2 is the absence of mixed reactants after the detonation front in CASE1, whereas CASE2 contains leftover H_2 after the detonation wave, although $I_{mix} = 0$. This demonstrates the existence of losses due to non mixed H_2 . Interestingly not even CASE1 is able to process 100% of the premixed reactants close to the interface of fresh gases and product gases of the previous detonation cycle.

Figure 9: Phase averaged temperature field of CASE1 (a) /CASE2 (b), phase averaged Y_{H_2} distribution of CASE1 (c) /CASE2 (d) and fields of I_{mix} for CASE1 (e) and CASE2 (f) along 33% span width of the annulus.

By analyzing the phase locked averages of the fields, a better understanding of the global flow features can be achieved. The field of Y_{H_2} of CASE1 (Fig. 9 (c)) shows that the maximum amount of fuel is at the bottom of the chamber (see Fig. 9 (c) 2) and then decreases downstream due to the intermittent presence of pockets of combustion products from the previous cycle

(see Fig. 9 (c) 1). The field of Y_{H_2} in CASE 2 shows three distinct regions (Fig. 9 (d)) in front of the detonation wave: 1) a rich area at the bottom of the chamber as a result of the injection of H_2 at the bottom, where the fuel does not have time to mix properly. After this first region, mixing then proceeds downstream leading to a decrease in Y_{H_2} . 2) a triangular area where Y_{H_2} decreases considerably. The low amount of Y_{H_2} in this region (Fig. 9 (d)), suggests that this region is filled with air coming from the air injection gaps. Finally, 3) a rich band of fuel close to the product of the previous cycle.

Taking into account I_{mix} in Fig. 9 (e), CASE1 displays an overall homogeneous mixing field of $I_{mix} = 1.0$, however bands with a low $I_{mix} < 1$ occur. They denote the presence of a diluted band of mixture, since the value of I_{mix} is fixed due to the premixing condition, allowing only the presence of combustion products to lower it. The presence of combustion products will naturally influence the propagation of the detonation, compromising the overall detonation efficiency. These bands can additionally be sources of deflagration burning resulting in another loss in fuel, hence a lower efficiency in the detonation. Fig. 9 (e) contains an additional band of a diluted reactant mixture above the black H_2 iso contour in the contact area of products of the previous detonation cycle and the fresh gases of the current cycle. The values below $I_{mix} = 1$ in Fig. 9 (e) result from less H_2 in this region, also shown in Fig. 9 (c).

Overall CASE2 differs considerably in terms of fuel distribution, compared to the uniform distribution of fuel in CASE1. A major difference in

Fig. 9 (c) and (d) is the previously observed tail of unburnt H_2 starting on the top of the detonation in CASE2. It shows that the mixture in Fig. 9 (d), zone 3) is too rich, which is demonstrated by Fig. 9 (f): in the area of the tail I_{mix} is zero. The index also has its highest value close to the face plate, as a result of the unmixed H_2 jets. Contrary to CASE1 the mixing field below the black iso contour in CASE2 for $\Theta \sim -\pi/2$ indicates more H_2 penetrating the chamber without being mixed with air.

The quality of mixing can be further investigated by plotting the probability density function of the mixing index I_{mix} . To do this we assume that a gas mixture at temperature $T \leq 500K$ corresponds to unburnt gases. We then plot the distribution of I_{mix} in this region.

Figure 10: Instantaneous and averaged qualitative PDFs of CASE1 and CASE2 for the fresh gases, declared at $T \leq 500K$. A vertical dotted line is positioned at $I_{mix} = 1$.

The averaged and instantaneous curves of these PDFs in Fig. 10 show

that the distribution of I_{mix} is qualitatively time independent for CASE1 and CASE2. The PDFs of CASE1 have a peak at $I_{mix} = 1$ due to the premixing. The minimum value is at $I_{mix} = 0.67$ showing that there is a small zone, where the premixed reactants are diluted by combustion products. Hence, during the refill process, combustion products are entrained and mixed with fresh premixed gases. CASE2 on the other hand displays a different distribution, due to the required mixing process. The peak occurs for a $I_{mix} = 0$. This reveals the presence of unmixed regions where at least one of the reactants is missing. Here I_{mix} spans over a range from 0 to 10, displaying the maximum possible range for I_{mix} in CASE2.

The range of I_{mix} and the peaks for $I_{mix} < 1$ of CASE2 in comparison with the PDF of CASE1 emphasize, that the mixing quality of CASE2 is very far from the optimal distribution, and explains its lower detonation speed. The PDF of CASE2 has a second peak around $I_{mix} = 0.65$. This means that in the chamber the effective global equivalence ratio is lower than the nominal one, hence the mixture predominantly burns in lean conditions. This confirms that mixing plays a major role in the efficiency of the combustor.

The cylindrical cuts of Fig. 9 do not show the radial distribution of the investigated cases. To understand the actual mixing and fuel consumption, two planes normal to the detonation propagation direction and shifted by ± 7.2 degrees with respect to the detonation plane are investigated for CASE 1 (Fig. 12) and CASE 2 (Fig. 13). These planes show the flow ahead (+7.2) and downstream (-7.2) the detonation front. Their position is shown in

Fig. 11. This angle is sufficiently small to allow for a qualitative analysis of the mixture state that the detonation burns.

Figure 11: Cut at $x = 10.6\text{mm}$ above the faceplate of the phase average of the field of temperature for CASE2 with the position of the cuts: the angle of the cuts with respect to the detonation front at -7.2 (dashed line) and 7.2 degrees in counterclockwise direction are represented by Fig. 12 and 13. The cuts with respect to the detonation front of 7.2 , 72 , 144 and 216 degrees are shown in Fig. 14. In this graph, y and z denote spatial coordinates. The detonation rotates in counterclockwise direction.

Figure 12 focuses on CASE 1. Fig. 12 (a) shows that in front of the detonation a refill of the inner span of the chamber extends to 35mm in height. Pre-detonation, as observed in [38], the chamber is not effectively flushed by the new reactants: only the inner span is fed with new reactants and a recirculation zone above the air inlet slot is formed, while the outer span width stays filled with combustion products (comb. products) of the previous cycle. Hence, no detonation can be achieved along the whole span width. The I_{mix} field (Fig. 12 (b)) pre-detonation has a homogeneous distribution in the fresh gas region with a decrease of I_{mix} in span wise direction for a span width of $> 50\%$. This is due to the increasing dilution of fresh gases by combustion products in span-wise direction. After detonation, the mixed reactants are

Figure 12: CASE1 - Phase locked averaged cuts in front and after the detonation front in pairings pre-and post-detonation: the first pair shows the temperature fields (a), the second I_{mix} (b), the third H_2 (c) and the last the H_2O fields (d). The dot-dashed line denotes the radial position of the previously displayed unwrapped cuts and the dotted line denotes 50% span width. A black (white in (d)) iso contour at $u = 0$ (axial downstream velocity) reveals a re-circulation zone R in front of the detonation. The colormaps are saturated as established, additionally the H_2O colormap is saturated at the maximum value for a stoichiometric reaction. The x -axis goes from Δ_{cc} , the outer wall to 0, the inner wall.

consumed and $I_{mix} = 0$. Due to non-ideal flushing of the chamber the fresh gases and combustion products of the previous cycle form a contact surface, which in turn becomes a source for parasitic combustion. The contact surface can be estimated to be at $0.1 \leq Y_{H_2O} \leq 0.15$ (Fig. 12 (d)). After detonation passage, the temperature distribution shows a higher temperature for a span width of $> 50\%$ than for the inner span of the chamber (Fig. 12 (a)). This cannot be a result of a detonation, since the amount of mixed reactants pre-detonation passing is too low for a span width of $> 50\%$. Instead, the shock wave attached to the detonation compresses the hot products of the previous cycle to these temperatures.

Figure 13 focuses on CASE2. The cuts in front of the detonation in e.g. Fig. 13 (a) reveal the same non-ideal flushing of the annulus as CASE1. This shows that the injected gas composition does not impact the overall refill behavior in the annular chamber. The inner half of the annulus is supplied with fresh gases, whereas the outer span (span width $> 50\%$) contains combustion products of the previous cycle. Fig. 13 (a) also shows a re-circulation zone formed above the air inlet. Contrary to CASE1 (Fig. 12 (b)) the distribution of I_{mix} in CASE2 (Fig. 13 (b)) is highly non uniform and reaches values $I_{mix} > 1$. The decrease of I_{mix} in span wise direction for a span width of $> 50\%$ again occurs due to the increasing dilution of fresh gases by combustion products in span-wise direction. In Fig. 13 (b) and Fig. 13 (c) a white dashed line marks the redirection of the axially injected fuel jets towards the inner wall, at an angle of ~ 30 degrees with respect to the face plate.

Figure 13: CASE2 - Phase locked averaged cuts in front and after the detonation front in pairings pre-and post-detonation: the first pair shows the temperature fields (a), the second I_{mix} (b), the third H_2 (c) and the last the H_2O (d) fields. The dot-dashed line denotes the radial position of the previously displayed unwrapped cuts and the dotted line denotes 50% span width. A black (white in (d)) iso contour at $u = 0$ (axial downstream velocity) reveals a re-circulation zone R in front of the detonation. The colormaps are saturated as established. The x -axis goes from Δ_{cc} , the outer wall to 0, the inner wall.

Before detonation passage, Fig. 13 (c) additionally reveals local pockets with high amounts of H_2 in the fresh gas area. In the re-circulation zone fuel gets entrained during refill and is mixed with combustion products of the previous cycle. The high mass fraction of H_2 at the bottom plate is caused by unmixed H_2 directly after injection. For a chamber length $0.01 \leq y \leq 0.02$, Fig. 13 (c) has a lean area in front of the detonation, due to bad mixing. After detonation passage (Fig. 13 (c)), unburnt H_2 can be found where the previously rich areas are found. The leftover fuel results from the detonation not being able to process it, since it did not mix with a sufficient amount oxidizer ((Fig. 13 (b) and (c), pre-detonation). The rest of the previously injected H_2 is consumed. Figure 13 (d) shows that the refill process again creates a contact surface between the fresh gases and combustion products of the previous cycle, introducing losses due to parasitic combustion. The contact surface can be estimated to be at $0.1 \leq Y_{H_2O} \leq 0.15$. The temperatures after detonation in the previously mixed area are below the high temperatures observed in Fig. 12(b), further emphasizing a non ideal detonation of fuel and oxidizer in the region, or an already advanced expansion after the detonation. The post-detonation plane of Fig. 13 (d) shows areas with low amounts of H_2O . This emphasizes that the detonation processes mainly lean mixtures and a significant amount of air preserves.

We have seen that the mixing assumptions (perfectly premixed vs. non premixed) play a major role. The next criterion for real injection (CASE2) is to know whether the SGS model used to model mixing plays a role. As

Figure 14: Q_μ on cuts performed on an representative instantaneous solution of CASE2 in front the detonation in increasing phase: (a)-(d) display the cuts at an offset of 7.2, 72, 144, 216 degrees in front of the detonation. The black dashed lines denote the respective maximum fill height and the vertical dashed line denotes the position of the unwrapped cuts previously shown. An additional white iso contour at $z = 0.5$ outlines the H_2 jets at the bottom of the chamber.

mentioned in Sec. 4.6 mixing in the LES approach is dependent on the turbulent viscosity ν_t (Eq. 5), imposed via the sub-grid scale turbulence model for LES. To confirm its influence we first compute the corresponding dynamic turbulent viscosity $\mu_t = \nu_t \rho$ and investigate the ratio of μ_t divided by μ_{lam} (Eq. 1), here called Q_μ , on a representative instantaneous snapshot, covering the refill area. For high values of Q_μ the mixing process is dominated by μ_t introduced via the SGS, whereas low values indicate a minor contribution of μ_t . The fields of Q_μ are provided in Fig. 14. The planes for CASE2 in Fig. 14,

show that the Q_μ has its highest values in the refill zone directly, due the occurring high amount of turbulence, resulting from the high velocity of the incoming fresh gases. The drop of Q_μ downstream is a consequence of the high temperatures in the burnt gases. Since μ_{lam} scales like $\sim (T/T_{ref})^{0.686}$, meaning that μ_{lam} increases by 4 to 5 times going from cold gases to hot gases. Particularly for CASE2, it emphasizes that the mixing of H_2 and air is the strongest at the bottom of the chamber and is dominantly governed by μ_t .

Figure 15: Qualitative PDF of Q_μ along different iso surfaces in the fresh gases at $T \leq 500K$ for a representative instantaneous solution. The left image (a) shows the PDF of Q_μ for $z = 0.0258$ and $Y_{H_2O} = 0.04$ of CASE1. The right image (b) represents CASE2 and adds $z = 0.5$ to include the mixing in the H_2 cross flow.

The influence of μ_t on the reactants in CASE1 and CASE2 is shown via PDFs of Q_μ along different iso surfaces in Fig. 15: $z = 0.0258$ (for $T \leq 500K$) as a representative for the ideally premixed fresh gas condition in CASE1 and CASE2. The magnitude of μ_t in the dilution process with H_2O

is represented by the distribution of Q_μ along the iso surface of $Y_{H_2O} = 0.04$, which corresponds to 17% of the maximum Y_{H_2O} for a premixed case, making it a good value to check mixing with H_2O . Additionally the PDF of Q_μ along $z = 0.5$ ($T \leq 500K$) is plotted for CASE2 to include the mixing process in the cross flow at the injection. Along the common iso surfaces in Fig. 15 (a) and (b) one finds the same behavior: Q_μ along $z = 0.0258$ has in both cases a similar peak around $Q_{\mu,CASE1,z=0.0258} = 12$ and $Q_{\mu,CASE2,z=0.0258} = 18$, hence mixing in the refill area is dominated by μ_t . The dilution process is also dominated by μ_t , with $Q_{\mu,Y_{H_2O}=0.04} = 6$ in CASE1 and $Q_{\mu,Y_{H_2O}=0.04} = 7$ in CASE2, is about a factor 2 smaller than seen for $z = 0.0258$.

Note that the temperature fields in Fig. 12 and 13 show instabilities in the shear layer of fresh and burnt gases. Due to the high temperature gradients (hence density gradients as well) between the two regions and fluctuations in the downstream velocity one can for the moment presume this to be a combination of Kelvin-Helmholtz (velocity gradient based) and Rayleigh-Taylor (density gradient based) instabilities. Another reason could be the interaction of the fresh gases with an acoustic mode, created by the detonation in the respective setup.

The comparison of CASE1 and CASE2 shows clearly that the design of the injection system is a major contributor to losses and an optimization of the injection system is detrimental for improving the operability of the RDE. First, a better flushing of combustion products is necessary to profit from the full span of the annular chamber and to minimize non-detonative combustion

in the contact area of fresh gases and hot combustion products. Second, it is important to maximize the mixing performance for a higher detonation efficiency.

6.3. Influence of the SGS model

A direct check of the effects of the SGS model is to change it. For this purpose we conduct an additional run CASE3, where CASE3 is run with the SIGMA model instead of the WALE model. The result on the pressure signals is displayed in Fig. 16.

Figure 16: Mid-span pressure signals of CASE2 and CASE3 at $y = 25 \text{ mm}$. The signals are recorded after a steady detonation propagation has been achieved and are sampled at a frequency of 3.8 MHz .

The pressure jumps corresponding to the passing detonation are superimposing each other, while the peak values differ from each other. This shows that the influence of SGS model does not impact the detonation speed, which implies that the influence of μ_t on the fresh gas mixing is not significantly

altered by the chosen SGS model. A comparison of the PDFs of CASE2 and CASE3 (Fig. 17), gives further insight on the influence of the SGS model. The respective curves all show peaks at similar values of Q_μ , where the relevant range is $5 \leq Q_\mu \leq 50$, which is present for both SGS. The position of the peaks of the curves for $z = 0.5$ are in agreements, as well as the peaks of $z = 0.0258$. This emphasizes that the SGS models apply μ_t in a very similar manner, making the sub-grid mixing highly similar. Overall, μ_t is one order of magnitude larger than μ_{lam} , which is generally accepted as an indicator of the reasonable impact of the SGS model on the results.

Figure 17: PDF of Q_μ along the iso contours of $z = 0.0258$ and $z = 0.5$ in the fresh gases at $T \leq 500K$ of CASE2 and CASE3.

The comparison of WALE and SIGMA shows that the influence of an adequately chosen SGS model does not impact the results in a significant way. Instead the focus must be shifted to optimizing the modeling of detonations and deflagrations in RDEs.

6.4. Efficiency comparison

The analysis of the overall efficiencies is conducted in 2 steps:

- Combustion: The efficiency E (Eq. (9)) is examined to see how much fuel burnt in the chamber.
- Detonation: The detonation index I_{det} (Eq. (10)) is introduced to distinguish the occurring reaction regimes and to obtain the detonation efficiency E_{det} (Eq. 15). This parameter identifies which percentage of the fuel consumption occurs in a detonation regime.

Figure 18: Top: Combustion efficiency of CASE1, CASE2 and CASE3 for 11 consecutive cycles. Bottom: probe pressure signals of the runs.

Combustion efficiencies are presented in Fig. 18. The combustion efficiency of CASE1 is the highest with over 99%. Due to premixing, the fresh gases can burn almost ideally, only being influenced by local dilution via H_2O . The combustion efficiency is also quite constant, which indicates a steady detonation propagation and fuel consumption. CASE 2 and CASE3

display lower efficiencies at 93%, showing that the combustion efficiency is heavily influenced by the mixing regime.

The development of E_{det} (Fig. 19) allows a similar conclusion: the pre-mixing in CASE1 results in more fuel effectively detonating. 80% of the consumed fuel is burnt in a detonation. On the other hand a considerable loss in detonation efficiency is observed with the non-premixed cases CASE 2 and CASE 3 (65% of the consumed fuel in average), due to mixing losses. CASE2 and CASE3 deliver not only the same D , but also overall the same E_{det} , implying a direct link between E_{det} and D .

Figure 19: Top: Detonation efficiency of the three investigated runs for 11 consecutive cycles. Bottom: probe pressure signals.

7. Conclusion

Three comparisons based on mixing assumptions and SGS models of the TUB RDE are conducted using fully compressible LES. The mixing assumptions allow to investigate the influence of the mixture composition on the

performance of the combustor and the SGS model comparison explores the influence of the SGS model on mixing. Three cases were computed: CASE1 (perfectly premixed), CASE2 (non premixed, SGS model = WALE) and CASE3 (non premixed, SGS model = SIGMA).

Each run delivers a single rotating detonation wave. However, different wave rotation frequencies with $8280Hz$ for CASE1 and $7630Hz$ for CASE2 and CASE3 are observed. The radial inward injection through the air slot leads to the formation of a re-circulation zone at the outer wall of the lower chamber and leads to mixing losses due to fresh gases being mixed into them. Phase average cuts before and after the detonation fronts show, for all cases, non-detonated fuel after the detonation passage due to the dynamics of the injectors, making the injection system the primary source of losses.

Two main mechanisms for the efficiency of the combustor are determined: first imperfect mixing leads to worse conditions for detonating the mixture and a consequential decrease in D . Secondly, dilution with product gases of the previous cycles compromises the optimal operation of the RDE. In the LES, the mixing is dominated by the μ_t imposed by the SGS, since it is at least an order of magnitude higher than the corresponding μ_{lam} . A change of the SGS has led to the same D , which makes the choice of the SGS less important as long as the SGS model is used accurately. Here WALE and SIGMA were used.

A detonation index I_{det} is introduced to distinguish detonation and deflagration regimes. The detonation efficiency E_{det} shows that premixing in-

creases the amount of fuel consumed in a detonation regime. The combustion efficiency E increases significantly and D increases as well. The detonation speed is linked to the mixing performance of the injection configuration and E_{det} is directly linked to D . At the same time, losses of 20% of burnt fuel in CASE1 and 30 – 35% of burnt fuel in CASE2 and CASE3 to deflagration are present, which highlights the requirement of a chemistry model able to capture the relevant detonation and deflagration parameters.

This kind of high-fidelity LES of RDEs can be used to improve the design of the injection system, since it properly models the mixing process. It shows the effects of blockage and the highly turbulent recovery process of the injectors can be better followed. A reasonable depiction of the mixing process in non-premixed RDE systems, and its underlying mechanism, including the consumption (and non-consumption) of fuel, are provided. This emphasizes the requirement of performing high-fidelity LES of reactive systems, since numerical investigations of cold flows neglect effects such as dilution, parasitic combustion or blockage due to detonation passage. In this context, the present study stresses the strong impact of the rotating detonation wave on the performance of the injection system, suggesting that cold flow simulations can only provide partial conclusions during the design process and urging the community to include the reactive waves very early during the design process.

8. Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have not known of any competing financial interests or personal relationships which might have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 956803 (INSPIRE - INSpiring Pressure gain combustion Integration, Research, and Education). This work was performed using HPC resources from GENCI-TGCC (Grant 2023 - A0132B10157). The help of Dr. Myles Bohon (TU Berlin) is gratefully acknowledged. We also express our gratitude to Ms. Provence Barnouin (TU Berlin) for conducting the experiment and providing the data for this work.

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